

**FOOD SAFETY: CHEMICALIZATION
OF FOOD AND ITS IMPLICATIONS FOR HEALTH**

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Abstract

Technology has permeated all aspects of our lives, food inclusive. The food that we consume in the modern day is highly chemicalized. This has a tremendous implication on our health, although chemicalization of food has come to stay with us but we still have a choice of healthy living. This paper discusses the various chemicals; both naturally occurring and artificial that find their way into our food. These include agricultural chemicals, food additives, preservative and phytotoxins. Discussion is made on their benefits and especially their negative implications on human health. It is recommended among others that these chemicals should be regulated by the appropriate government agency.

Keywords: *Food safety, Chemicalization, Implication and Health.*

Introduction

Food is essential for the existence of man just like the air we breathe and the water that we drink (Begun, 2007). The survival and maintenance of human body hinges on food in-take, this is the basic substance that is needed in the body system for adequate growth and body maintenance (Tunyich, 2011). Food is basically chemical molecules of various types and forms, since

the body system can only utilize it in these simplified forms, it is needed to be taken in the right proportion to make the body system function optimally where it undoubtedly influences the health of man, in terms of the kind and amount consumed (Ajala, 2006).

Food substances occur naturally in the form of carbohydrates, proteins, fats and oils as organic macro-molecules (Nick 2010). Minerals, vitamins and water are the inorganic form in which food substances occur (Taylor et-al. 2007). The food substances mentioned above are all naturally occurring; they are either synthesized through photosynthesis or absorbed from the soil by the primary producers in a food chain. They are beneficial to the consumer when eaten in the appropriate proportion; excessive consumption of these naturally occurring food substances may lead to conversion and storage as harmless substances in the body or outright excretion from the body (Ajala, 2006).

The artificial synthesis and introduction of these substances in the form of food additives, agricultural chemicals, fatteners, sweeteners, etc poses a health challenge to the consumer (Roday, 2008).

According to (Begun, 2007) nutrients are chemical substances derived from food by the body and the health of a person depends on the types and quality of foods he chooses to make his diet, hence man is a product of nutrition.

Men in recent times due to the dictates of modernization have modified ways in which food is prepared and preserved. Several kinds of additives are added to food for enhancement to the taste bud and aesthetic (beauty) value of the food; these additives and preservatives are chemical substances that are either synthesized or are naturally occurring; they have various health implications. Although it is imperative to store food either as raw or processed to prevent spoilage, it is still worthy of note to consider the implication on human health which may not be noticed on time (Ajala, 2006).

Chemicals that found their way into Food

Technology and chemicals define modern life, mankind and his progress. Chemicalization of food began centuries ago because more food was needed to feed ever increasing populations. At the same time, concern was generated to keep unhealthy chemicals out of our diet (Kroger, 2005), who further cited the US Department of Agriculture (1979) that chemicals occur in food either as residue (remnants from agricultural chemicals), additives (deliberately added) and even as naturally occurring toxicants. Some find their way into our food through chemically treated water and even utensils used in preparing the food.

It is a fact that every bit of every piece of food is composed of chemicals; for instance, a cup of milk, a bite of bread or a cup of coffee contains thousands of chemicals; invariably nutrients are made up of chemicals. (Hutton, 2002). He further asserted that most of the hundreds of thousands of chemicals are neutral in character, some (quite a few) are toxic. Of course, we know about poisonous mushrooms which are naturally occurring, there are also toxic alkaloids in potatoes or sulphur compounds in onions. There is practically no substance we currently use as food and consume that is not chemicalized for one reason or the other. Technological processes are the major 'culprit'; water treatment, agricultural technological practices, pharmaceuticals, modern catering processes, etc.

Some common but harmful chemicals

Chlorides

Calcium chloride is found in a variety of snacks, beverages, sports drinks and specialty items as a preservative (Robin, 2010), who also asserted that calcium chloride prevents food spoilage, and also provides the essential mineral calcium, which increase nutritional quality of food product and due to

increased concerns about high sodium content of foods and lack of adequate calcium intake, calcium chloride is added by manufacturers to food products which gives it a slightly salty taste instead of sodium chloride or table salt.

Ingestion of calcium chloride may seriously irritate the moist linings of the body, such as those in the nostrils, mouth and throat, lips, eyelids and ears. Larger dose may induce gastrointestinal upset, vomiting and abdominal pain (Benzaquen, 2011).

Fluorides

Water supply is fluoridated; this is meant to retard the growth of plaque bacteria that causes dental caries (Granville & Knight, 1952) by poisoning the bacteria with fluoride. Fluoride is a strong enzyme poison. However, the fluoridation of our water supply and the liberal use of fluoride toothpaste introduce dangerously high concentrations of fluoride in a very active and toxic form. Fluoride is associated with higher rates of birth defects, cancer and immunosuppression, lower IQ of children, dental and skeletal fluorosis, and neurological (mental) problems. It has also been shown to cause increased bone fractures, cataracts and infant mortality (Walker 2000).

Aluminum

Aluminium is used to precipitate impurities in our drinking water. Its presence in drinking water causes health problems. It may also be ingested in some brands of baking powder, and free-flowing salt, or from aluminum hydroxide antacid medications. Aluminum easily dissolves in weak acids, which are present in fruits, tomatoes, cucumber, and beets. Acidic foods that come in contact with aluminum surfaces are injurious to health. Even tap water or rainwater can be acidic. Food cooked in aluminium pots or in aluminium foil, can absorb aluminium because aluminium dissolves into food and water during the cooking process and goes into the bloodstream and accumulates

in different organs in different people causing a multitude of effects. Some unpleasant effects of eating food cooked in aluminium are hyper-acidity, indigestion, flatulence, skin problems like pigmentation, eczema, dandruff and chronic inflammation of the intestine, which may be diagnosed or misdiagnosed as Ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease or as chronic amoebic dysentery. Aluminium reduces growth of bone and predisposes to osteoporosis (Hiranandani 2011)

Aluminium compounds have been reported to interfere with the absorption of essential minerals such as calcium and phosphate, although the extent to which this occurs at dietary exposure levels is unclear and soluble aluminium compounds have demonstrated reproductive toxicity (FAO/WHO 2006).

Heavy metals Mercury, Cadmium, Nickel, Arsenic, Zinc and Lead

Mercury poisoning is the focus here and may result from certain pesticides and fungicides, laxatives, large predatory fish meals and even amalgam tooth filling substances. The amalgam becomes eroded over a long period due to chewing of acidic food substances, it may also chip off bit by bit and becomes lodged in the stomach, and this may be absorbed and stored in body fat, especially in the brain. According to food information.net (2012) mercury toxicity from foods is very rare and nearly always caused due to environmental pollution (aquatic) where it is ingested by shrimps, lobsters, etc. It has a number of effects on humans, which can be simplified into the following; disruption of the nervous system, damage to brain functions, DNA damage and chromosomal damage, allergic reactions, resulting in skin rashes, tiredness and headaches, negative reproductive effects, such as sperm damage, birth defects and miscarriages. According to Hiranandani (2011) mercuric poisoning from amalgam could cause degradation of learning abilities, personality changes, tremors, vision loss, deafness, loss of muscle co-ordination and memory loss, multiple sclerosis, chronic fatigue

syndrome, and depression.

Chemical residues

These include remnants of category of chemicals used in pest control, animal husbandry in agriculture, preservatives and industrial chemicals appearing as chronic or sporadic environmental pollutants. Modern technology is responsible for the presence of all of these unwanted chemicals in our food; hence, it is important to fully understand the risks and benefits of the substances that human ingenuity has invented to work for us. The risk-benefit balance of agricultural chemicals tilts heavily towards benefit. All agricultural pesticides that are poisonous enough to kill pests are equally hazardous to humans, hence caution should be maintained in handling them (Roday, 2008). Further more; countries where pesticides are not used lose a large percentage of their food to insects and other pests.

Heavy metals such as lead, mercury, and arsenic, which are constituents of agricultural chemicals are always persistent; since they are basic elements and cannot be further broken down and destroyed in the environment.

The reality of agriculture has made chemicalization of our food inevitable. Likewise the use of steroid hormones and antibiotic in animal husbandry has greatly increased supply and breeding. These chemicals are not without their down sides, they are found as residue in animal and plant products in which they have been applied with their attendant health implications.

Naturally occurring toxicants

Mother-nature herself is not completely benign; there are naturally occurring chemicals in food, especially from plants, occurring as phytochemicals. Many of which are beneficial to human physiology (Ajala, 2006); by eliminating

toxins acquired as by products of metabolism. Some of these phytochemicals are toxic to man and may produce gastrointestinal disturbances which may sometimes prove fatal (Marzia & Catherin 2001).

Beneficial Phytochemicals

- Bulforaphane prevents cancer and it is found in cauliflower, kale, broccoli, cabbage, sprouts and mustard green.
- Isoprenoids: it is also associated with lowering the risk of cancer, they are found in certain fruits, vegetables, cereal grains, citrus oils, etc.
- Flavourides: they are antioxidants that reduces the risk of heart disease, they are found in tea, onion, apples and wine.
- Phytosterols and tocotrienols: reduces cholesterol level in the body, they are found in barley, wheat, corn and variety of seeds.

Toxic Phytochemicals

- Trypsin inhibitors: found in soy beans, where they inhibit breakdown and availability of proteins in the digestive system which results into intestinal disorder. This inhibitor could be destroyed by adequate heat treatment.
- Solanin: found in damaged potatoes is toxic to man. It causes vomiting, abdominal pain and diarrhoea.
- Egrot (a parasitic fungus) attacks wheat, rye grain and barley causing egotism. Bread made from such infected cereal may cause convulsion and gangrene.

Process-induced toxicants

There is cause for concern about possible chemical interactions and toxic products formed during food processing, these include refrigeration, pasteurization, canning, etc. Several chemicals are formed during these

processes, some harmful; example are polycyclic aromatic amines (PAAs) in grilled/barbecued meat, N-nitrosamines in cured meat and fish and heterocyclic aromatic amines (HAAs) in over-heated meat and fish and some beneficial; examples are in cocoa, tea and coffee processing (Stadler & Lineback 2008).

Toxicants formed in the body

Several toxicants are formed in the body (depending on the constituent of the food) from the metabolic processes; they are derived from the break-down of the food we eat with the aim of cleansing the system. The body has several systems, most importantly the liver, kidneys and lungs, they change chemicals to a less toxic form (detoxify) and eliminate them. These toxicants must not accumulate in the body. (Rosenberg & Yomashiro, 2008) Example of these are ammonia, urea, etc.

Food additives

Food additives are substances added to food to make it more attractive, in terms of beauty and flavour, and to preserve it (Ajala, 2006)

Foods that taste good are high in calories and quick to prepare, they are referred to as Junk food, and they have little nutritional value (Philip, 2010). While most people have their own list of foods that they would consider as junk food, it generally refers to foods that are high in sugar (such as soda pop, candy, ice cream and most pastries), high in fat (particularly, saturated fat such as burgers, pizza, hot dogs, French fries and most fried foods) and high in salt.

But the preceding list is not all-inclusive. For example, most would consider the imitation juice on the market today as healthy. However, these products

Are loaded with sugar, artificially flavoured, and contain very little pure juice. Many foods that we consider healthy could in fact be considered as junk food. However, it is not necessarily harmful to eat these foods occasionally and in moderation, the contrary has devastating effect on health (The Real Truth Magazine 2004). All food additives must comply with government safety regulation before use (Marzia and Catherine 2001).

Common additives and their health implication

Artificial sweeteners: has been linked to increased levels of obesity due to the way fructose is metabolized in the body and lipid abnormalities that cause diabetes and increased risk of heart disease (Ajala, 2006). Aspartame, saccharine, etc are substitutes for sucrose (sugar) with more side effects on health than natural sugars. Saccharine is associated with liver and bladder cancer. Aspartame is the sweetener commonly used in diet cokes and other diet drinks, its use can cause neurological ailments, multiple sclerosis, muscle spasms, insomnia, etc. (Hiranandani 2011).

Monosodium Glutamate (MSG): MSG (Ajinomoto, etc) is a common ingredient in fast foods, Chinese foods, canned food, frozen food, prepared meals, sauces, salad dressing, cheeses chips and a multitude of other foods. They are excitotoxins of glutamic acid salts (taste or flavour enhancers). Glutamate is a neurotransmitter that is present in the extra-cellular fluid in very low concentration, increased level inappropriately causes neurons abnormality, and at higher levels, brain cells begin to die. Oxygen deficiency and hypoglycaemia both interfere with the energy production of brain cells to make them susceptible to damage by these excitotoxins. This may be an important factor in the development of neurological diseases. Most processed

foods contain excitotoxins, especially when they contain commercial taste or flavour enhancers, such as hydrolyzed vegetable protein, soy protein extract, commercial soups, sauces and gravies are usually most it is associated with boosting the appetite by stimulating insulin production, thus causing obesity, and diabetes mellitus. It is also a common trigger for headaches, migraine and elevated blood pressure. Consumption of MSG has a strong link with stomach and colon cancer (Hiranandani, 2011).

Trans and Hydrogenated Fats: These are synthetic fat molecules that have been chemically altered through hydrogenation or cooking at high heat. They cause problems at the cellular level. The most common foods are deep fried, processed and commercially baked products. They are known to increase the risk of death from a heart attack by 25% (Philip, 2010).

Conclusion

In as much as we need to preserve our foods, make them pleasant and attractive we should take into cognizance the health implication of our actions. It is said that we are what we eat; what ever our health situation, it has direct correlation with what we consume. We are a product of technological advancement, though we have been enslaved by it, we should strike the risk-benefit balance of this and our health.

Recommendation

Several chemicals that are used for the storage of agricultural produce, herbicides, pesticides, chemicals used in water treatment and even food additives and preservatives should be regulated by the government. Sensitization should be carried out to the general populace from time to time

on the benefits and hazards of these chemicals. In addition to the regulation of agro-chemicals, the correct application and the detoxification period should be taught to the farmers to reduce or prevent incident of residue poisoning, since their usage in modern time is inevitable. Slow and long term poisoning which is the result of chemical residue accumulation in the body system is preventable if adequate precautions are taken by reduction of use or complete stoppage of their use. It will be highly beneficial if only natural remedies are used in agro-processes and only natural spices are used as food additives and preservatives.

Conclusion

In as much as we need to preserve our foods, make them pleasant and attractive we should take into cognizance the health implication of our actions. It is said that we are what we eat; what ever our health situation is, it has direct correlation with what we consume. We are a product of what we eat. Chemicalization of food has led to the development of technological advancement, though we have been enslaved by it, we should strike the risk-benefit balance of this and our health.

Recommendation

Several chemicals that are used for the storage of agricultural produce and in the production of brain cells in the brain are highly toxic and even food additives and preservatives should be regulated by the government. Sensitization should be carried out to the general populace from time to time.

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